

CORENEXT

Press Release

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European Core Technologies for Next Generation Communication-Computing Hardware

In an era where digital transformation is paramount, Europe stands at the forefront of innovation, poised to strengthen its digital capabilities and lead the charge towards a more connected and technologically advanced future. At the heart of this endeavour lies COREnext, a pioneering collaborative initiative that marks its first-year anniversary with a resolute commitment to anticipating the technological developments required for future 6G networks.

6G use cases offer great benefits to the European economy and society, and the intended 6G applications will permeate people's personal life and will be deployed in critical infrastructure. For that reason, European capabilities in that field will be of high importance to ensure high levels of data privacy, security and contribute to EU's digital sovereignty. COREnext brings together major European representatives from the telecommunication and semiconductor industries to meet these goals.

COREnext will develop a trustworthy-by-design platform and thus answer the need for European capabilities for B5G/6G computing based on a new architecture for base stations. This architecture will efficiently and securely integrate third-party accelerators capable of supporting even the most demanding 5G/6G processes in cloud servers, base stations, and client-side devices. COREnext will strengthen its European position beyond B5G/6G RAN disaggregated architectures by adding trustworthy-by-design digital and analogue components.

The project brings together major telecommunications and microelectronics players and academic research partners across 10 EU countries to realise these goals by December 2025. **COREnext** adopts a strong interdisciplinary approach: having different academic disciplines working together with industry collaborators to integrate knowledge and methods to develop and meet shared goals, achieving a real synthesis of approaches. A strategic roadmap will offer a transparent path towards the future exploitation of the generated research results, fostering a continuing European strategy for emerging European digital capabilities in this communication-computing domain.

COREnext is a joint initiative by Barkhausen Institut, Australo, Chalmers University, CEA, Ericsson, Cyberus Technology, EURECOM, Infineon Technologies, imec, NXP Semiconductors, Radiall, Sequans Communications, Technische Universität Dresden, TIM, WINGS ICT Solutions, IMS Research Center, ETH Zurich, IHP, Nokia Germany, Nokia Network France, III-V Lab, Infineon Technologies, and KALRAY.

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